

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Twenty-four-month effortful control predicts emerging autism characteristics

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Abstract

Longitudinal research can assess how diverging development of multiple cognitive skills during infancy, as well as familial background, are related to the emergence of neurodevelopmental conditions. Sensorimotor and effortful control difficulties are seen in infants later diagnosed with autism; this study explored the relationships between these skills and autism characteristics in 340 infants (240 with elevated familial autism likelihood) assessed at 4–7, 8–10, 12–15, 24, and 36 months. We tested: (1) the relationship between parent-reported effortful control (Rothbart's temperament questionnaires) and sensorimotor skills (Mullen Scales of Early Learning), using random intercept cross-lagged panel modelling; (2) whether household income and maternal education predicted stable individual differences in cognition; (3) sensorimotor and effortful control skills as individual and interactive predictors of parent-reported autism characteristics (Social Responsiveness Scale) at 3 years, using multiple regression; and (4) moderation of interactions by familial likelihood. Sensorimotor skills were longitudinally associated with effortful control at the subsequent measurement point from 12–15 months. Socioeconomic status indicators did not predict stable between-infant differences in sensorimotor or effortful control skills. Effortful control skills were longitudinally related to 3-year autism characteristics from the first year of life, with evidence for an interaction with sensorimotor skills at 24 months. Effects of effortful control increased with age and were particularly important for infants with family histories of autism. Results are discussed in relation to different theoretical frameworks: Developmental Cascades and Anterior Modifiers in the Emergence of Neurodevelopmental Disorders. We suggest a role for 24-month effortful control in explaining the emergent autism phenotype.

KEYWORDS

autism, development, effortful control, infancy, sensorimotor skills, socioeconomic status

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Research Highlights

- Sensorimotor skills longitudinally predicted effortful control from 12–15 months onward but effortful control did not longitudinally predict sensorimotor skills during infancy.
- Measures of effortful control skills taken before the age of 1 predicted continuous variation in autism characteristics at 36 months, with associations increasing in strength with age.
- Effortful control (measured at 12–15 and 24 months) was a stronger predictor of 36-month autism characteristics in infants with elevated familial likelihood for autism.
- The relationship between 24-month sensorimotor skills and 36-month autism characteristics was stronger in infants with weaker effortful control skills.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Autism is a neurodevelopmental condition defined by differences in social communication, specific interests, repetitive behaviours, and sensory sensitivities (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). The presentation is highly heterogeneous and, in addition to the core symptoms, autistic children frequently experience co-occurring anxiety, ADHD and language difficulties (Mannion & Leader, 2013). At present, autism cannot be reliably diagnosed until at least 2 years of age. However, the infant sibling approach has significantly advanced understanding of possible earlier markers of autism and how they relate to the eventual behavioural phenotype (see Elsabbagh & Johnson, 2016; Szatmari et al., 2016, for reviews).

The infant sibling approach follows children from birth who have an older sibling with autism (EFL; elevated familial likelihood) or typical familial likelihood (TFL; no first-degree relatives with autism). Up to 20% of children who have a sibling with autism experience clinical level symptoms, compared to only 1%–2% of the general population (Ozonoff et al., 2011; Palmer et al., 2017). Many other siblings of children with autism show subthreshold clinical symptoms (Sucksmith et al., 2011), a behavioural profile referred to as the broader autism phenotype (Le Couteur et al., 1996). Compared to TFL infants, EFL infants also show difficulties in skills such as perception, attention and motor control, and social communication (e.g., Leonard et al., 2014; Stone et al., 2007) that are frequently impacted in children with autism diagnoses (Elsabbagh & Johnson, 2016). Hence, studying EFL children makes it possible to assess cognitive domains relevant to autism before canonical symptoms emerge in a relatively large sample.

Infant sibling research has shown that the autistic phenotype is more likely a result of divergent development in perceptual, attentional, motor, and social systems than social brain network-specific differences (Elsabbagh & Johnson, 2016). This conclusion was based on numerous behavioural and neuroimaging studies indicating differences in multiple sensory and cognitive systems in EFL infants and inconsistent evidence relating to possible focal differences in brain networks dealing with social cognition (e.g., Clifford et al., 2013; Flanagan

et al., 2012; Lewis et al., 2014; Paul et al., 2011; Wolff et al., 2015, although see Glauser et al., 2022; Gui et al., 2021; Guy et al., 2018; Tye et al., 2022 for evidence of early face processing differences). However, to our knowledge, no studies have explored how cognitive systems interact across infancy to influence the emergent autism phenotype.

The developmental precursor to executive function, effortful control (EC), represents one important possible domain of investigation. EC is the use of attention and inhibitory control to deliberately regulate emotions and behaviour (Rothbart et al., 1994). In infants, it is often measured by asking parents to observe infant behaviours such as interacting with an object for an extended period of time, following instructions and returning to calm after becoming distressed. EC is subserved by frontal brain regions which rapidly develop during early infancy and come to exert significant control over behaviour by as early as 12 months of age (Johnson & de Haan, 2015). The transition from EC to more mature (although still developing) cognitive control, executive function, is thought to be complete by the end of third year of life (Hendry et al., 2016).

Studies have shown that EC in very young EFL children is not at the level expected for their developmental stage, with individual differences in this ability stable across the first 3 years of life (Clifford et al., 2013; Macari et al., 2017). EC measured at 24 months is predictive of levels of autism characteristics 1 year later (Garon et al., 2016). Further, there is evidence linking EC contemporaneously to some specific characteristics associated with autism including the ability to filter incoming sensory information (Adams et al., 2015) and preference for sameness (Uljarević et al., 2017).

Several studies also suggest possible developmental inter-relations between infants' EC skills and their wider cognitive profile. In a longitudinal study of EFL and TFL infants, Ersoy et al. (2021) showed that strong EC skills in infancy were associated with lower subsequent levels of anxiety in toddlerhood and a cross-sectional study by Nakagawa et al. (2016) indicated that EC is positively associated with sensory and motor abilities in typically developing 3-year-olds. This latter finding is worth investigating further as it may be relevant to the emergent autism phenotype; differences in sensorimotor skills in EFL compared

to TFL infants are, like EC difficulties, apparent from very early in life. Research using the Mullen Scales of Early Learning (MSEL; Mullen, 1995), a behavioural assessment tool that taps motor, language, and perceptual abilities, shows emerging EFL/TFL differences in perceptual skills from around 6 months of age, which become more pronounced over time (Estes et al., 2015). By between 12 and 48 months, lower scores on all MSEL subscales are observed for infants who go on to be diagnosed with autism (Burns et al., 2013; Estes et al., 2015; Landa & Garrett-Mayer, 2006).

Developmental Cascades theory suggests that achieving sensorimotor developmental milestones has cascading effects on cognitive development (Bradshaw et al., 2022). These competencies are suggested to be foundational for the development of more complex cognitive skills, as they allow children to learn through exploration of and exchange with their social and physical worlds (Libertus & Hauf, 2017). In this view, delays in or disruptions to motor and perceptual development may constrain the development of EC. EC then goes on to influence further development of the lower-level systems and vice-versa. Divergent development in these different systems is thought to have cumulative effects on the emergent autism phenotype (Bradshaw et al., 2022). If this view is correct, one would expect stronger associations between the latest measures of cognitive skills and autism characteristics than between the earliest cognitive measures and autism characteristics.

An alternative framework—Anterior Modifiers in the Emergence of Neurodevelopmental Disorders (AMEND)—offers a competing account of the role of different cognitive systems in explaining autism characteristics (Johnson et al., 2021). This approach, proposed by several of the authors of the present study, suggests that higher order cognitive abilities subserved by anterior (frontal) brain regions can modulate the relationship between atypical early development of lower-level cognitive skills and later autism characteristics. Applying this to explain previously documented associations between EC, sensorimotor skills and autism characteristics, developing EC might influence the impact of sensorimotor differences on behavioral outcomes. AMEND therefore predicts that EC moderates the effect of sensorimotor skills on autism characteristics and that greater levels of EC difficulties should align with higher levels of autism characteristics. This is yet to be tested.

Whilst the modulating effect of skills like EC may also promote individual differences in neurotypical individuals, AMEND expects these effects to be weaker (Johnson et al., 2021). This is because strong EC is proposed to moderate the effect of earlier emerging perturbations in sensorimotor development. This modulating potential is therefore more relevant for EFL infants than TFL infants. If this is correct, then one would expect moderation of the interaction between EC and other areas of cognition by familial history of autism. To our knowledge, no study has yet tested this possibility.

Evaluating and contrasting the Developmental Cascades and AMEND approaches to cognitive development can help to elucidate how the autistic phenotype emerges over infancy. Developmental Cascades theorists predict bidirectional influence between sensorimotor skills and EC (Figure 1a) and additive effects on later autism character-

istics (Figure 1b). AMEND predicts that EC interacts with sensorimotor skills to influence autism characteristics (Figure 1b) and that this will be stronger in EFL infants (Figure 1c), whilst Developmental Cascades theorists make no such predictions. Identifying how and when trajectories diverge between EFL infants will have important theoretical implications for our understanding of the early markers of neurodevelopmental conditions.

When taking a systems-level approach, the role of the environment must also be considered. Familial socioeconomic status (SES) has repeatedly been shown to predict cognitive skills across childhood (Last et al., 2018) and there is evidence that SES associates with EC (Lecheile et al., 2020) and motor development (Ferreira et al., 2018) during toddlerhood. However, SES is rarely considered in infant sibling studies and neither the Developmental Cascades (Bradshaw et al., 2022) nor AMEND (Johnson et al., 2021) models of autism, in their current forms consider the possible influence of SES on developing cognitive skills.

It is frequently observed that parental occupation and education level have distinct associations with cognitive skills during childhood (e.g., Hackman et al., 2015; Conway et al., 2018; Waters et al., 2021). It is therefore likely that they influence cognitive development through different mechanisms, for example chronic stress versus exposure to enriching materials and caregiver interactions respectively (e.g., Ursache & Noble, 2016). Hence, we wanted to look at the roles of both dimensions of SES in this study. Here we do not use a genetically informed design, so our findings should be taken with the understanding that complex genetic effects (e.g., gene-environment correlations and shared genetic variation between children and parents) which influence child development and parental nurturing may partly explain any observed SES effects.

The present study aims to better understand how EC and sensorimotor skills are related over development, how SES relates to these cognitive measures, and the relation of EC and sensorimotor skills to later autism characteristics. We used random intercept cross-lagged panel models to look at the developmental interrelations between EC (measured by parental questionnaires) and sensorimotor skills (MSEL) between 4–36 months. This statistical approach assesses both contemporaneous and longitudinal within-person associations between multiple variables (Hamaker et al., 2015). We also tested whether stable between-person variation was explained by maternal education level and/or household income. Using multiple regression, we then tested whether EC and sensorimotor skills have additive or interactive associations with autism characteristics. Finally, we explored whether elevated familial likelihood for autism strengthens interactions between EC and sensorimotor skills on autism characteristics. Data were from the British Autism Study of Infant Siblings project (BASIS; <http://www.basisnetwork.org/>).

We hypothesized that EC and sensorimotor skills would be bidirectionally related across the first 3 years of life (H1), per the Developmental Cascades framework. We further predicted that including SES as a time invariant covariate would improve model fit (H2i), given the small to moderate associations observed between SES and cognitive skills elsewhere (Korous et al., 2020). We hypothesized

FIGURE 1 Diagrams illustrating predictions of Developmental Cascades (grey arrows) and AMEND (black arrows) about (a) longitudinal associations between effortful control and sensorimotor skills, (b) longitudinal associations between effortful control, sensorimotor skills and autism characteristics and (c) interactions between effortful control and sensorimotor skills in predicting autism characteristics. For ease of illustration, only two timepoints are shown. N.B. Converging arrows with a star represent an interaction effect. No arrows indicates that the framework does not make predictions about this process.

that there would be differences in the strengths of the SES variables' associations with the random intercepts of sensorimotor skills and EC (H2ii), replicating findings that parental education level and household income have different associations with developing cognitive skills in older children (Conway et al., 2018; Hackman et al., 2015; Waters et al., 2021).

Since very early behavioural measures are rarely reliable predictors of later autism characteristics (Elsabbagh & Johnson, 2016; Wolff & Piven, 2021), we anticipated some point of divergence in both sensorimotor and EC skills where they would begin to significantly predict autism characteristics (H3i). Because of measurement lag time and that autism characteristics are more readily detectable by the second year of life, we expected that, by 24 months, these measures would signif-

icantly predict autism characteristics (H3ii). As a test of AMEND, we hypothesized that EC and sensorimotor skills would have interactive, rather than additive effects on social responsiveness (H4). Additionally, we hypothesized that familial likelihood for autism would moderate interactions between EC and sensorimotor skills (H5; Johnson et al., 2021).

As a sensitivity check, we reran the models substituting language for sensorimotor measures. These analyses are detailed in the Supplementary materials and Tables S5–S7. Language is not thought to be a low-level cognitive skill, so these models were run to ascertain how confident we should be that our results are explained by developmental interactions between high and low-level systems.

2 | METHOD

2.1 | Participants

Data were from three phases of BASIS, a prospective longitudinal cohort study of EFL and TFL children ($N = 381$). One hundred and three infants were recruited in phase 1, 143 in phase 2 and 135 in phase 3. A total of 340 infants were included in the following analyses ($n = 240$ EFL). Infants were first assessed when they were aged 4–7 months, then again at 8–10 months, 14 months, 24 months, and at 36 months.

Three infants were excluded as they were half siblings. A further 37 infants with elevated likelihood for ADHD as well as autism were excluded. Since autism + ADHD is associated with a qualitatively different cognitive profile to autism without ADHD (Taurines et al., 2012) we did not want to introduce additional variability into our cognitive measures for EFL infants and lacked the statistical power to consider infants with EFL for autism + ADHD separately.

Finally, one infant was excluded because they were a multivariate outlier. We used the *modi* (version 0.1.0) package's BACON-EEM algorithm to check for multivariate outliers in the cognitive and Social Responsiveness Scale data. This allows for outlier detection in datasets containing missing data. This method is described in Bill and Hulliger (2016). We set the alpha value to be $0.01/n$ as this is recommended for large datasets in the user manual (Hulliger & Sterchi, 2018) and a cut point of MD distance > 61.39 was chosen by the algorithm.

There were slightly more males (51%) than females in the whole sample, but this difference was not statistically significant $\chi^2(1) = 0.11$, $p = 0.745$. Importantly, the sex distribution was not significantly different for EFL (51% male) and TFL (45% male) infants, $\chi^2(1) = 0.74$, $p = 0.389$. Forty-one EFL infants were diagnosed with autism at 36 months (18% of EFL infants with data on autism diagnosis), 73% of whom were male, while no TFL infants had received an autism diagnosis.

2.2 | Measures and procedure

Figure 2 shows the measures taken at each timepoint which are described in detail in the sections below.

2.2.1 | Motor, language and perceptual skills

The MSEL (Mullen, 1995) was used to assess the verbal and non-verbal developmental level of participating infants at each timepoint. The MSEL is a standardised behavioural assessment for 0–68-month-old infants. It assesses five key developmental domains: gross motor, fine motor, and visual reception (non-verbal) and receptive language and expressive language (verbal). The MSEL has good internal, test–retest and inter-rater reliability (Mullen, 1995). We used the sensorimotor composite score, derived from the fine motor and visual reception scales, as our indicator of non-verbal developmental level.

2.2.2 | Effortful control

EC was measured by Rothbart's temperament questionnaires. The Orienting/Regulatory Capacity (ORC) subscale from the Infant Behavior Questionnaire–Revised (Gartstein & Rothbart, 2003) was our measure of EC from the first measurement point to 15 months, at 24 months it was the Effortful Control subscale of the Early Childhood Behaviour Questionnaire (Putnam et al., 2006) and at 36 months we used the Effortful Control subscale of the Children's Behaviour Questionnaire (Rothbart et al., 2001). The version of these questionnaires used (i.e., full, short form, very short form) depended on the phase of the study infants were participating in (Supplementary Materials). The short and very short forms of these questionnaires include subsets of questions from the long form questionnaires and retain the same subscales. One-way ANOVAs showed no significant effects of phase on EC scales at the five timepoints (smallest $p = 0.063$). Hence, we did not adjust for the version of the questionnaires administered at each timepoint. See Supplementary Materials for full descriptions of the questionnaires.

Previous studies in neurotypical samples using the shortest versions of the temperament questionnaires employed in the present study have shown that Cronbach's alphas for the EC subscales, or the traits comprising those subscales, range from 0.62 to 0.84 (Putnam et al., 2010; Putnam et al., 2014; Putnam & Rothbart, 2006). Internal consistency for the effortful control subscales in the EFL participants in the present study ranged from $\alpha = 0.63$ –0.98. Please see Supplementary materials and Table S1 for further details on internal consistency of the EC subscales.

2.2.3 | Autism characteristics

Data from the Preschool Form of the Social Responsiveness Scale Second Edition (SRS-2; Constantino, 2012) were available for participating children at 36 months. This 65-item parent report measure assesses the presence of and degree to which autism characteristics are apparent in everyday life and has been validated for use with children from 2.5 to 4.5 years of age. The SRS-2 has high internal consistency ($r = 0.94$ –0.96), adequate inter-rater reliability ($r = 0.61$ –0.77), and good construct validity (Bruni, 2014).

The raw total score is converted to a T-score based on gender and age. In this study we use the T-score as a continuous measure of autism characteristics.

2.2.4 | Socioeconomic status

Two measures of SES were included in this study: maternal highest education level and total annual household income. Table 1 shows the sociodemographic composition of the whole sample and the sample split by familial history of autism. Caregivers indicated which education ($\leq 16/A$ -Level or equivalent/undergraduate/postgraduate)

FIGURE 2 Diagram showing the study design and key measures.

TABLE 1 Sociodemographic information of the included participants.

	Whole sample	Elevated familial likelihood	Typical familial likelihood
Mother's highest level of education	n = 306	n = 211	n = 95
Up to 16 years	11 (4%)	7 (3%)	4 (4%)
Up to 18 years/vocational qualification	68 (22%)	55 (26%)	13 (14%)
Undergraduate degree	118 (39%)	87 (41%)	31 (33%)
Postgraduate/professional qualification	109 (36%)	62 (29%)	47 (49%)
Household income*	n = 322	n = 226	n = 96
< £20,000	28 (9%)	22 (10%)	6 (6%)
£20–40,000	74 (23%)	63 (28%)	11 (11%)
£40–60,000	81 (25%)	63 (28%)	18 (19%)
£60–80,000	46 (14%)	31 (14%)	15 (16%)
>£80,000	93 (29%)	47 (21%)	46 (48%)

N.B. Percentages are expressed as the proportion of infants with data for that variable.

and household income categories (minimum: <£20,000; maximum: £80,000+; with £20,000 increments) they belonged to in a questionnaire administered at study entry. Despite there being up to a 12-year difference in the time at which different families reported on SES, there was no significant effect of phase on household income ($F(1, 332) = 0.11, p = 0.742$) so we took this to be a meaningful indicator of the included families' relative wealth.

The median annual pre-tax income for this sample was £40,000–£60,000 (based on information provided between 2006–2018) with the majority of the TFL families living in London, whilst the median

annual household income was £30,677 in London and £27,901 in the UK in 2018 (Tower Hamlets Corporate Research Unit, 2018). Also, only 34% of UK adults hold a Bachelor's degree or a higher level of qualification (Office for National Statistics, 2023) compared to 75% of our sample. Our sample was therefore relatively affluent.

There were significant between-groups differences in the relative distribution of maternal education level ($\chi^2(3) = 13.34, p = 0.004$) and of household income ($\chi^2(4) = 28.41, p = 0.001$). TFL families more frequently appeared in the highest education category and income category (Table 1).

2.3 | Data cleaning and preparation

All participants were assessed at 24 and 36 months, however there were between-phase differences in the ages at which they were assessed before 24 months. To deal with this, we created the following age categories: 4–7 months, 8–10 months, and 12–15 months. Since phase 1 participants were then left with missing data on the EC scale and sensorimotor composite either at 4–7 or 8–10 months, we then used MICE (version 3.15.0) to impute values for these measures using predictive mean matching. Age category creation is further outlined in Table S2. All other variables were unlikely to be missing completely at random, so we chose not to impute these to avoid reducing the variance around these measures. Instead, we used full information maximum likelihood estimation for all models. Since very few infants had mothers who finished their education at 16, this category was collapsed with the educated up to 18 category.

2.4 | Statistical analysis

All models were run in Rstudio 4.3.1 (2023-06-16 ucrt).

2.4.1 | Random intercept cross-lagged panel models

The Lavaan (version 0.6-18.2001) RCLPM() function was used to run random intercept cross-lagged panel models to test our first two hypotheses. Models were constructed following Mulder and Hamaker's (2021) specifications. Model 1a was an unconstrained model testing whether there were bidirectional within-person cross-lagged associations between EC and MSEL sensorimotor composite (hypothesis 1), controlling for stable between-person differences. Model 1b was an extension of this model with household income and maternal education level included as time invariant covariates.

The models included within-person centred EC and sensorimotor skills at all five timepoints (4–7 months, 8–10 months, 12–15 months, 24 months, 36 months) and thus had four directional paths from EC to EC at the subsequent measurement point, four directional sensorimotor-sensorimotor paths, five non-directional paths between EC and sensorimotor skills at each measurement point, four directional paths from EC at one measurement point to sensorimotor skills at the next and four directional paths from sensorimotor skills to EC at the subsequent measurement point.

Both of our random intercept cross-lagged panel models were run with 4–7-month and 8–10-month data imputed. Models were rerun without imputed data and these results are reported in Supplementary Materials. Fit indices which have less of a penalty for model complexity than their counterparts (CFI rather than TLI and AIC rather than BIC) are reported, given the exploratory nature of this study. As it is standard practice, we also report the RMSEA but note that this is prone to type 2 error in small samples (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Though there is some disagreement about what threshold values should be used, according to all widely cited recommendations, CFI values < 0.90 and

RMSEA values > 0.10 indicate poor model fit (Browne & Cudeck, 1992; Hu & Bentler, 1999; Schumacker & Lomax, 2010). We also report χ^2 goodness of fit estimates/df for cross-lagged panel models and interpret values < 5 as acceptable following (Wheaton et al, 1977). For CFI and RMSEA, we report robust estimates.

2.4.2 | Multiple regression models

We used Lavaan's sem() function to run multiple regression models testing hypotheses 3–5. Four models were run (one for each predictor variable measurement point) to test the hypotheses that sensorimotor skills and EC would predict later autism characteristics (H3i) by 24 months (H3ii). Each model had two predictors, the main effects of sensorimotor and EC skills:

$$\text{Autism characteristics 36m} \sim \text{effortful control} + \text{sensorimotor skills}$$

To test hypothesis 4, that EC modulates the effect of sensorimotor skills on autism characteristics, we added 2-way interactions between the sensorimotor composite and EC to the models at each timepoint:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Autism characteristics 36m} \sim & \text{effortful control} + \text{sensorimotor skills} \\ & + \text{effortful control} * \text{sensorimotor skills} \end{aligned}$$

Finally, 3-way interactions between sensorimotor skills, EC and familial likelihood status were added to test the prediction that the modulatory effect of EC is stronger in EFL infants (H5) as well as the main effect of familial likelihood and 2-way interactions between familial likelihood status and the cognitive predictors:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Autism characteristics 36m} \\ \sim & \text{group} + \text{effortful control} + \text{sensorimotor skills} \\ & + \text{effortful control} * \text{sensorimotor skills} + \text{group} * \text{effortful control} \\ & + \text{group} * \text{sensorimotor skills} + \text{group} * \text{effortful control} * \text{sensorimotor} \\ & \text{skills} \end{aligned}$$

Since hypotheses 3–5 were concerned with longitudinal associations of EC and sensorimotor skills with autism characteristics measured at 36 months, we did not run models with 36-month sensorimotor skills and EC as predictors. We report AIC, R^2 and coefficients for models with imputed data. We also report whether comparable results were observed when the models were rerun without imputed data.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Descriptives

TFL infants scored, on average, significantly higher than EFL infants from 8–10 months onward on the EC scales and at 4–7, 12–15, 24 and

FIGURE 3 Mean (\pm SE) scores on (a) the effortful control subscale and (b) Sensorimotor Composite by group. N.B. * = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$. 4-7- and 8-10-month values are pre-imputation. Between group comparisons were carried out using Welch's unpaired t -test.

36 months on the MSEL sensorimotor composite (see Figure 3). Scores on the EC scale were fairly stable over time and MSEL scores tended towards increasing over time.

EFL infants scored significantly higher on the Social Responsiveness scale ($M = 49.68$, $SD = 12.36$) and had a larger range of scores than the TFL group ($M = 42.22$, $SD = 3.66$), $t(269) = 7.74$, $p < .001$. Table 2 shows the correlation matrix for all variables of interest.

3.2 | Hypothesis 1

We used random intercept cross-lagged panel modelling to test hypothesis 1: that EC would predict later sensorimotor skills and vice-versa. Figure 4 gives a path diagram of the model (1a). Model fit according to the Comparative Fit Index and χ^2/df was acceptable (Table 3). The random intercepts of EC and sensorimotor skills were significantly correlated. All but the first two sensorimotor–sensorimotor associations and the final EC–EC lagged association were significant. Significant cross-sectional EC–sensorimotor skills associations were

seen at 4–7, 24 and 36 months. Cross-lagged sensorimotor to EC skills associations were significant from 12–15 months. Cross-lagged results were unchanged rerunning the model without imputed data at 4–7 months and 8–10 months (see [Supplementary materials](#)).

We did not find evidence of bidirectionality to support hypothesis one. All the cross-lagged paths which were significant went from sensorimotor skills to EC. Results from this model were thus only partially consistent with the predictions of the Developmental Cascades framework.

3.3 | Hypothesis 2

To test hypotheses 2i and 2ii, we reran the random intercept cross-lagged panel model, including household income and maternal education as time invariant covariates (model 1b; Figure 5). We predicted that including SES time invariant covariates would improve the fit of the model (H2i) and that maternal education and household income would differ in their associations with EC and sensorimotor skills (H2ii).

TABLE 2 Correlation matrix of all the variables included in our analyses.

a													
1. Group													
2. Maternal education	-0.27***												
3. Household income	-0.19***	0.34***											
4. Effortful control 4-6 m	-0.01	0.10	-0.08	Effortful control—effortful control									
5. Effortful control 8-10 m	-0.17**	0.05	0.04	0.56***									
6. Effortful control 12-15 m	-0.18**	0.08	-0.01	0.37***	0.63***								
7. Effortful control 24 m	-0.20***	0.14*	0.01	0.26**	0.46***	0.55***							
8. Effortful control 36 m	-0.19***	0.08	0.09	0.17*	0.16*	0.25***	0.35***						
9. Sensorimotor composite 4-6 m	-0.21**	0.01	-0.01	-0.06	0.03	0.01	0.13	0.14	Sensorimotor—sensorimotor				
10. Sensorimotor composite 8-10 m	-0.10	0.06	0.12*	-0.08	0.01	0.05	0.12	0.17**	0.37***				
11. Sensorimotor composite 12-15 m	-0.22***	0.00	0.07	-0.04	0.05	0.09	0.21***	0.14*	0.51***	0.44***			
12. Sensorimotor composite 24 m	-0.31***	0.23***	0.21***	0.05	0.03	0.12*	0.31***	0.27***	0.20*	0.26***	0.43***		
13. Sensorimotor composite 36 m	-0.25***	0.20***	0.19**	-0.10	-0.12	0.01	0.21***	0.26***	0.07	.030***	0.32***	0.60***	
14. Autism characteristics 36 m	0.31***	-0.27***	-0.18**	-0.12	-0.24***	-0.33***	-0.58***	-0.30***	-0.15	-0.12	-0.22***	-0.36***	-0.32***

N.B. The table shows the strength of parametric correlation coefficients for bivariate relations using pairwise complete observations. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$. 4-7- and 8-10-month value are pre-imputation.

FIGURE 4 Path diagram showing the cross-lagged panel model (1a) testing developmental inter-relations between within-person centred effortful control and sensorimotor skills (model 1). N.B. Single headed arrows indicate regression coefficients with standardised betas. Double headed arrows indicate correlation coefficients. Dashed lines are used for non-significant paths.

TABLE 3 Fit indices for models 1a and 1b.

	χ^2/df	CFI	RMSEA	AIC
Model 1a	3.71	0.93	0.10	13,987
Model 1b	13.88	0.88	0.10	13,856

N.B. Model 1a. had had directional paths from effortful control to effortful control at the subsequent measurement point (x4), directional sensorimotor-sensorimotor paths (x4), cross-sectional sensorimotor-effortful control paths (x5), and cross-lagged paths from effortful control to sensorimotor skills (x4) and vice versa (x4). Model 1b included maternal educational level and household income as time invariant covariates of the random intercepts.

FIGURE 5 Path diagram showing the cross-lagged panel model including maternal education and household income as covariates (model 2). N.B. Single headed arrows indicate regression coefficients with standardised betas. Double headed arrows indicate correlation coefficients. Dashed lines are used for non-significant paths.

This model had unacceptable fit and fit the data worse than model 1 according to the χ^2/df and CFI values (Table 3).

Neither maternal education, nor household income significantly predicted the random intercepts of sensorimotor or EC skills. Adding these covariates did not reduce the strength of cross-lagged paths, showing that the longitudinal associations between sensorimotor and EC skills were not accounted for by SES. These results were replicated in the non-imputed dataset (Supplementary materials).

These results do not support H2i as model fit worsened. H2ii was also not supported since neither SES index was a significant predictor of stable between infant differences in EC or sensorimotor skills.

3.4 | Hypothesis 3

We predicted that at a certain stage in infant development, EC and sensorimotor skills would begin to predict autism characteristics (H3i). We expected the variables would be associated with autism characteristics by 24 months (H3ii). To test these predictions, we ran four main effects multiple regression models looking at longitudinal associations of sensorimotor skills and EC with autism characteristics. Models explained up to 39% of the variance in autism characteristics with variance explained increasing with the age at which cognitive measures were taken. Table 4 gives the R^2 value for each timepoint and the parameter estimates.

EC significantly predicted later autism characteristics from the first measurement point, with beta values substantially increasing in strength with the age at which EC was measured. Sensorimotor skills were a significant predictor of autism characteristics from 12–15 months (Figure 6).

To confirm that our results were not due to imputation, we reran the 4–7 month and 8–10-month analysis without the imputed EC and sensorimotor data. The significant effect of 8–10-month EC on autism characteristics observed with the imputed data did not change in strength or direction and remained significant at $p < 0.001$ (Table S3). However, the effect of 4–7-month EC on autism characteristics was smaller and non-significant in the non-imputed data.

H3i and H3ii were therefore fully supported for EC and sensorimotor skills, as both significantly associated with later autism characteristics from a specific point in development (8–10 months for EC and 12–15 months for sensorimotor skills) and this occurred by 24 months.

3.5 | Hypothesis 4

Hypothesis 4 proposed that the effects of EC and sensorimotor skills on autism characteristics are interactive, not additive. To test this, we added a 2-way interaction to each of the four main effects models (models 3a-d). Variance explained increased slightly at all time points

TABLE 4 Model statistics and parameter estimates for predictors in models 2 (additive effects model) and 3 (interaction effects model).

Model	Effortful control		Sensorimotor composite		2-way interaction		R ²	AIC
	β	B (CIs)	β	B (CIs)	β	B (CIs)		
a. 4–7 m								
Model 2	–0.18**	–2.75 (–4.72, –0.78)	–0.03	–0.04 (–4.72, –0.78)			0.03	1764
Model 3	–0.18**	–2.76 (–4.73, –0.79)	–0.03	–0.04 (–0.21, 0.13)	–0.01	–0.12 (–1.36, 1.12)	0.03	1593
b. 8–10 m								
Model 2	–0.22***	–3.69 (–5.66, –1.72)	–0.11	–0.12 (–0.25, 0.01)			0.06	2100
Model 3	–0.23***	–4.00 (–5.97, –2.02)	–0.12	–0.13 (–0.26, 0.00)	0.13*	1.36 (0.08, 2.64)	0.09	2022
c. 12–15 m								
Model 2	–0.32***	–5.84 (–7.83, –3.85)	–0.20***	–0.22 (–0.34, –0.10)			0.15	2102
Model 3	–0.32***	–5.85 (–7.84, –3.86)	–0.20***	–0.22 (–0.34, –0.10)	0.01	0.15 (–1.18, 1.48)	0.15	2052
d. 24 m								
Model 2	–0.54***	–9.22 (–10.95, –7.50)	–0.18**	–0.19 (–0.30, –0.08)			0.39	1868
Model 3	–0.52***	–8.81 (–10.56, –7.07)	–0.17**	–0.17 (–0.28, –0.06)	0.12*	1.23 (0.24, 2.21)	0.40	1717

N.B. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$.

FIGURE 6 Bar chart showing the beta coefficients for the associations of effortful control and sensorimotor skills measured at different timepoints with autism characteristics measured at 36 months. N.B. Error bars give 95% CIs.

except 12–15 months and relative fit indices indicated superior fit for the interaction models in all cases (Table 4). Models explained up to 40% of the variance in autism characteristics (Table 4), with variance explained increasing with the age at which cognitive measures were taken.

However, the interaction effect only reached significance at 24 months. Figure 7 shows that higher EC at 24 months was again associated with fewer autistic characteristics at 36 months. This effect was stronger in infants who showed lower sensorimotor scores. No other interactions were significant; please see Table 4 For details of these effects.

These results provide evidence consistent with hypothesis 4 at 24 months, but suggest that earlier in development, the effects of sensorimotor and EC skills on autism characteristics are more independent.

3.6 | Hypothesis 5

Finally, we reran the interactive regression model, including familial likelihood status (model 4) to test H5: that familial likelihood sta-

TABLE 5 Comparative fit statistics and variance explained for 3-way interaction models.

Model	AIC	R ²
2a. 4–7 months	1083	0.14
2b. 8–10 months	1933	0.17
2c. 12–15 months	1963	0.22
2d. 24 months	1393	0.46

N.B. Models regressed group, effortful control, sensorimotor composite, group*effortful, group*sensorimotor composite, effortful control*sensorimotor composite, and group*effortful control*sensorimotor composite on 36-month autism characteristics.

tus would moderate interactions between EC and sensorimotor skills. Models explained up to 46% of the variance in 36-month autism characteristics, with variance explained increasing with age at which cognitive measures were taken (Table 5).

No 3-way interactions were significant (Table 6), contrary to hypothesis 5. However, there were significant 2-way interactions between familial likelihood status and EC measured at 12–15 and 24 months.

FIGURE 7 Interaction plot showing the significant 2-way interaction between 24-month effortful control and sensorimotor skills on 36-month autism characteristics. N.B. The graph shows a median split (median = 53) for sensorimotor skills where high = greater than the median score and low = below the median score for ease of interpretation. The grey bands around the lines reflect 95% CI.

As Figure 8 shows, EC skills were a strong negative predictor of autism characteristics in EFL infants, but there was virtually no relationship between EC skills and autism characteristics in TFL infants. The main effect of familial likelihood status was also significant in all models, with TFL infants showing lower levels of autism characteristics. No other associations were significant (see Table 6 For coefficients for all predictors in model 4). When we replicated these analyses without data imputed at 4–7 and 8–10 months, results were unchanged (see Table S4).

4 | DISCUSSION

This study aimed to test and, where relevant contrast, the predictions of Developmental Cascades (Bradshaw et al., 2022) and Anterior Modifiers in the Emergence of Neurodevelopmental Disorders (AMEND; Johnson et al., 2021) regarding the relation between early cognitive skills and later autism characteristics. Firstly, we established whether a composite of sensorimotor skills (Mullen Scales of Early Learning; MSEL) and parent reports of infant EC were related over the first 3 years of life using random intercept cross-lagged panel modelling. Sensorimotor skills significantly longitudinally predicted EC skills from 12–15 months, but there was no evidence for bidirectionality. Stable between infant differences in these two skill domains were related and were not predicted by maternal education level or household income.

Multiple regression analyses showed that having stronger EC and sensorimotor skills during infancy was associated with fewer later

autism characteristics. The relationship between EC and 36-month autism characteristics increased with age and was large and more than double that of sensorimotor skills by 24 months. We found evidence to suggest that sensorimotor and EC skills had independent effects on autism characteristics in the whole sample and that the relation between EC and autism characteristics was much stronger in EFL than TFL infants at 12–15 and 24 months. We also showed that EC moderated the relationship between sensorimotor skills at 24 months and autism characteristics, such that the relationship was weaker when EC skills were stronger. In summary, we found that sensorimotor skills predict later EC skills from 12–15 months of age and that EC and sensorimotor skills additively and interactively predict emerging autism characteristics.

As a specificity check, given that Developmental Cascades and AMEND make predictions about high- and low-level cognitive skills, we reran these models substituting MSEL language composite scores for sensorimotor scores (Supplementary materials and Tables S5–S7). Results from random intercept cross-lagged panel modelling revealed some important differences: Language began to predict EC from an earlier stage in development (8–10 months) and household income was related to stable between-infant differences in language skills. That we found that SES predicts individual differences in an autism enriched cohort, demonstrates the importance of considering SES in the context of cognitive development and should urge greater consideration of environmental factors in the study of neurodevelopmental differences. Regression analyses (covarying language skills and interaction terms containing language skills with household income) showed that, while both EC and language skills longitudinally predicted 36-month

FIGURE 8 Interaction plot showing the interaction between (a) 12–15 month and (b) 24-month effortful control and familial likelihood status on 36-month autism characteristics. Grey bands around the lines reflect 95% CI.

autism characteristics, adding interactions between EC and language worsened the fit of the model to the data.

These results contrast in a number of ways from the results obtained for sensorimotor skills. They therefore provide weight to the interpretation that the longitudinal relationships we observed between sensorimotor and EC skills may be a result of the influence of low-level and high-level systems on one another over development, as per Developmental Cascades and AMEND. Below, we evaluate the extent to which the findings from our models including sensorimotor skills support these two theories.

4.1 | Evaluating the evidence for Developmental Cascades and AMEND

4.1.1 | Developmental Cascades

Developmental Cascades proposes that higher order cognitive skills, like EC, are built upon lower-level skills (e.g., perceptual and motor skills; Bradshaw et al., 2022; Libertus & Hauf, 2017). Models supported this aspect of the theory, as sensorimotor skills significantly predicted later EC from 12–15 months onwards. This may be because good motor

TABLE 6 Coefficients for the association of the predictors with 36-month autism characteristics in the 3-way interaction model (model 4).

Model	Group	Effortful control	Sensorimotor composite	Effortful control × sensorimotor composite	Group × effortful control	Group × sensorimotor composite	3-way interaction
a. 4–7 months							
β	0.30***	-0.10	-0.03	-0.11	-0.10	0.06	-0.13
B (CIs)	7.20 (4.46, 9.94)	-1.47 (-5.19, 2.24)	-0.04 (-0.34, 0.26)	1.05 (-1.76, 3.86)	-1.35 (-4.50, 1.80)	0.73 (-2.26, 3.73)	-1.42 (-4.52, 1.67)
b. 8–10 months							
β	0.29***	-0.04	0.01	-0.01	-0.16	-0.09	0.15
B (CIs)	7.16 (4.47, 9.85)	-0.70 (-5.05, 3.66)	0.01 (-0.23, 0.26)	-0.13 (-3.09, 2.83)	-2.06 (-5.22, 1.10)	-1.15 (-4.15, 1.85)	1.73 (-1.53, 4.98)
c. 12–15 months							
β	0.27***	0.01	-0.04	-0.05	-0.32**	-0.12	0.04
B (CIs)	6.58 (3.81, 9.35)	0.18 (-3.89, 4.24)	-0.04 (-0.28, 0.19)	-0.62 (-3.50, 2.27)	-4.19 (-7.00, -1.39)	-1.58 (-4.31, 1.15)	0.60 (-2.66, 3.84)
d. 24 months							
β	0.24***	-0.02	-0.06	0.04	-0.52***	-0.06	0.03
B (CIs)	5.77 (3.32, 8.23)	-0.33 (-4.49, 3.83)	-0.06 (-0.33, 0.20)	0.44 (-3.11, 3.98)	-6.45 (-9.40, -3.51)	-0.75 (-3.85, 2.36)	0.35 (-3.35, 4.04)

N.B. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

and perceptual skills are important for developing an understanding of the environment and of causality through exploration, laying the foundations for EC development (Ghassabian et al., 2016; John et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2017). However, once developed, Developmental Cascades also assumes that EC should influence the development of other cognitive systems (Bradshaw et al., 2022). We did not find any evidence to support this during the first 3 years of life; none of the cross-lagged associations between EC and sensorimotor skills were significant. Perhaps this bidirectionality does not come into action until later in development when EC is maturing into executive function. Results were unchanged controlling for socioeconomic status, showing that the longitudinal associations between sensorimotor and EC skills are not explained by covariance between socioeconomic status and these skills.

We next tested the Developmental Cascades prediction that cognitive skills predict later autism characteristics and found, consistent with the theory, direct effects of motor, language, and perceptual skills and EC on autism characteristics from specific points in development over the first 3 years of life. Whilst previous studies show that the MSEL can differentiate between infants/young children with and without autism (Akshoomoff, 2006; Burns et al., 2013; Cheong et al., 2022), our results suggest that the MSEL sensorimotor composite is also sensitive to continuous variation in autism characteristics.

Surprisingly, we found that EC measures taken before infants were 1 predicted 36-month autism characteristics. This was unexpected for two reasons. First, previous studies have shown that behavioural markers of autism are not readily apparent in the first year of life (Elsabbagh & Johnson, 2016; Wolff & Piven, 2021). This could be because most previous studies have focused on autism diagnosis as a binary outcome, thus limiting the sensitivity of their analyses to detect, what we observed to be, small effects before the age of 1; see Licari et al. (2021) for an example where 9–14 month fine motor skills predicted autism characteristics (on a scale of 1–3) 6 months later. Second, it has been previously unclear whether frontal systems dealing with complex cognitive skills have a substantial influence on behaviour this early in life, since a shift toward more frontal control of behaviour does not occur until around the end of the first year of life (Johnson & De Haan, 2015). If our findings were replicated, they could prove valuable in terms of informing caregivers about what they might expect from the child as they develop based on early behaviours.

Despite the presence of significant early effects, the strength of the effects of EC on autism characteristics increased with age in the present study. This could index the cumulative effects of these developing cognitive systems on behaviour as postulated by Bradshaw et al. (2022). Alternatively, seemingly age effects may be due to the increasing closeness in time at which the cognitive measures were taken to the measure of autism characteristics. In any case, it is noteworthy that only EC, and not sensorimotor skills effects, increased with age. Using a different measure of EC, Garon et al. (2016) found a similarly strong ($\beta = 0.48$) effect of EC at 24 months on autism characteristics measured at 36 months in EFL infants. Our findings, alongside Garon

et al.'s, suggest 24 months might be a particularly significant period for EC skills to influence later autism characteristics.

4.1.2 | AMEND

The core prediction of AMEND (Johnson et al., 2021) is that strong activity of cognitive systems (e.g., EC) subserved by frontal brain regions can reduce the association of early-stage processing difficulties with autism characteristics. Since EFL infants are more likely to experience sensory-motor atypicalities, AMEND expects these effects to be stronger in EFL infants, and the modulation of early-stage processing difficulties by systems subserving cognitive processes like EC is thought to push EFL infants towards an outcome that is more comparable to neurotypical infants.

Consistent with AMEND's prediction, we found a small but significant interaction between EC and sensorimotor skills at 24 months and that adding an interaction term between sensorimotor and EC skills improved the fit of all regression models. The association of 24-month sensorimotor skills with autism characteristics at 36 months was weaker in infants with high EC scores, suggestive of modulation. Earlier interactions did not reach statistical significance. Hence, the three criteria for identifying anterior modifiers are met for EC: (1) Anterior modifiers become increasingly related to later autism characteristics over early development; (2) they are negatively related to neurodivergent outcomes; (3) they statistically moderate the relationship between lower-level cognitive skills and neurodivergent outcomes.

It should be noted, however, that the MSEL sensorimotor composite and the EC subscale of Rothbart's temperament questionnaires measure, to some extent, overlapping skills. By contrast, modification, as per AMEND, is usually thought about in relation to relatively independent skills. Some of what we captured with the MSEL is, therefore, likely to reflect EC, resulting in a dilution of the interaction effects. We may also, for this reason, have underestimated the motor, language, and perceptual skills of EFL infants, thus artificially inflated cross-sectional associations between EC and sensorimotor skills. EFL infants frequently experience EC difficulties and so may have found it more difficult to engage with the MSEL assessment (Akshoomoff, 2006). To provide a more robust test of the AMEND modification hypothesis, future studies should focus on predictor measures less likely to involve overlapping skills (see for example Carter Leno et al., 2022). Future research may also wish to use specific measures of sensory processing as the moderated variable, to provide a stronger operationalisation of what is intended by AMEND.

Although we did not find evidence that the moderating effect of EC on sensorimotor skills was stronger in EFL infants, we did observe that familial likelihood moderated the effect of EC on autism characteristics. Specifically, strong EC skills measured at 12–15 and 24 months were associated with lower levels of autism characteristics at 36 months, only in the EFL group. These results replicate and extend Garon et al.'s (2016) findings to show that EC is also an important predictor of 36-month autism characteristics in EFL infants as early as

12–15 months. Since we did not find comparable effects when using 4–7 month or 8–10-month cognitive predictors, this effect appears to be later emerging. Our results suggest these results are unlikely to be explained by the modulating effects of EC on sensorimotor and language skills. However, they could also be interpreted as indirect evidence for AMEND if EFL is a proxy for early sensory differences; in this case, we would be unlikely to observe a three-way interaction between group, sensorimotor skills, and EC.

4.2 | SES effects

The results from this study contribute to a growing understanding of factors influencing individual differences in skills that are related to autism. Consistent with research in older children (e.g., Conway et al., 2018; Hackman et al., 2015; Waters et al., 2021), we found that maternal education and household income had different associations with developing cognitive skills. Specifically, we found that household income was associated with between-infant differences in language skills, but not EC or sensorimotor skills, and that maternal education was not a significant predictor of between-infant differences in either measure. These results are consistent with the finding that language skills are more strongly associated with SES than other aspects of cognition (Noble et al., 2004, 2007) and the meta-analytic finding that language skills are not heritable but are substantially influenced by environmental factors (Austerberry et al., 2022). Since, in the present study, household income was reported by the parent and the MSEL is a behavioural observation that was carried out by the research team, this finding is particularly notable and cannot be attributed to shared measurement variance.

Bivariate correlations (Table 2) corroborated the finding that SES was not related to stable between-infant differences in EC, showing only one weak significant association at any time point across both indices. However, it is noteworthy that we did not find that SES explained between-infant differences in sensorimotor skills, since there were small but significant bivariate correlations between both SES indicators and sensorimotor skills toward the third year of life. This suggests that SES effects on sensorimotor skills may not be detectable until late infancy.

Further, effect sizes for associations between SES and executive function tend to be larger in more socioeconomically diverse samples (Lawson et al., 2017). We may, therefore, have underestimated the extent to which household income influences individual differences in cognitive skills, especially if income effects are non-linear and stronger up to a certain threshold. Income effects might also operate in quite a different way in infants with family histories of autism. For instance, parents may stop working when they would not otherwise to care for their autistic child. Therefore, the mechanism(s) of income effects might be expected to diverge for EFL compared to TFL infants more so than for parental education level. Since we considered EFL and TFL infants together, this variability may have diluted meaningful associations between household income and different aspects of cognitive development.

4.3 | Limitations and directions for future research

EC and autism characteristics were measured differently to motor, language, and perceptual skills. This may have introduced confounds in terms of the method of assessment and who rated behaviours. Firstly, reports of typical behaviour outside the lab are more ecologically valid. The MSEL provides just a snapshot impression of the infant's capabilities at that age, which are likely to vary naturally due to arousal levels but also could be influenced by anxiety in a less familiar setting with less familiar adults. However, the questionnaire responses could have been influenced by possible differences in sensitivity of EFL mothers to autism characteristics because they already have an autistic child and are more likely to themselves be neurodivergent (e.g., Rommelse et al., 2010). The MSEL also has the relative strength that it cannot be influenced by the social desirability bias. These relative strengths and limitations may have meant that we underestimated the associations between EC and sensorimotor skills.

That said, the use of both questionnaire and behavioural measures avoided shared method variance which would have been a stronger threat to the interpretation of our findings regarding EC-sensorimotor relationships. The same cannot be said for the relationships between EC and 36-month autism characteristics. Both were parent reported and may therefore have been subject to the same factors influencing reporting accuracy such as maternal reading comprehension. However, average maternal education levels were high in this sample and maternal education was only significantly associated with EC scores at 24 months. This correlation was half the size of the correlation between maternal education and 36-month autism characteristics, showing that mothers' ability to comprehend the questionnaire items is unlikely to have systematically influenced the observed relationships between EC and autism characteristics.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

This study has shown that a composite of motor and perceptual skills longitudinally predicts EC skills from 12–15 months of age and that both aspects of cognition, even before 1.5 years of age, predict 36-month autism characteristics. These results are partially consistent with Developmental Cascades, although this theory predicts bidirectional relations between different aspects of cognition. We also found that household income was a significant predictor of stable between infant differences in language skills, but not EC or sensorimotor skills, suggesting differential sensitivity of different aspects of cognition to SES during early development. We also, to our knowledge, offer the first test of the hypothesis (Johnson et al., 2021) that EC modifies the relationship between difficulties with sensorimotor skills and later behavioural outcomes and find some support for this theory. We show that EC, sensorimotor and language skills independently predict autism characteristics and that EC measured at 12–15 and 24 months is a particularly strong predictor of autism characteristics in infants with family histories of autism.

These findings contribute to an emerging body of evidence (see also Carter Leno et al., 2022; Fish et al., 2021) in support of AMEND, encouraging others to adopt this framework when studying the development of autism characteristics. They go some way to explaining the heterogeneity in outcomes of the infant siblings of autistic children and suggest that EC may play an important role in this respect. The evidence presented here could be used to inform early screening programmes and therefore reduce the negative consequences of late autism diagnosis for socioemotional (Mandy et al., 2022) and academic outcomes (Clark et al., 2018).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors confirm that they have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The datasets used in this study are stored in the British Autism Study of Infant Siblings (BASIS) Network Data Repository. The conditions of our ethics approval do not allow for public archiving of the pseudonymised study data. Data cannot be fully anonymized due to the nature of combined sources of information, such as sociodemographic and clinical outcome measures, making it possible to attribute data to specific individuals, and hence, falling under personal information, the release of which would not be compliant with GDPR guidelines unless additional participant consent forms were completed. Our data sharing procedures were created in consultation with stakeholders (Begum-Ali et al., 2023). To access the data, interested readers should contact the BASIS network coordinator at basis@bbk.ac.uk. Access will be granted to named individuals following formal ethical procedures governing the reuse of sensitive data. Specifically, requestors must pre-register their proposal, and clearly explain the purpose of the analysis to ensure that the purpose and nature of the research is consistent with that to which participating families originally consented. Additionally, requestors must complete and sign a data sharing agreement to ensure data is stored securely. Approved projects would need to adhere to the network's policies on Ethics, Data Sharing, Authorship and Publication. Please refer to the BASIS data sharing policies

available at <https://www.basisnetwork.org/collaboration-and-project-affiliation/index.html> for further details on the data access process and requirements. Legal copyright restrictions prevent public archiving of Mullen Scale of Early Learning and Social Responsiveness Scale-2 and which can be obtained from the copyright holders in the cited references. No part of the study procedures or analysis plans was preregistered prior to the research being conducted.

ETHICS STATEMENT

Ethical approval was granted by the London Central NREC: Ph1 – 08/H0718/76, Ph2 – 06/MRE02/73, Ph3 – 13/LO/0751. This project adhered to the BASIS network's policies on Ethics, Data Sharing, Authorship and Publication (<https://www.basisnetwork.org/collaboration-and-project-affiliation/index.html>). R.C.P. completed a data sharing agreement and project affiliation form to allow her to process and securely store the data.

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